

Challenges and solutions for sharing data and models in Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessments

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Outline

1. Quantitative microbial risk assessment: Uses and challenges
2. Analyzing the current practices for sharing data and models in QMRA
3. Solutions to improve

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Science-based decisions in microbial food safety

Food policy: from a hazard-based approach to a risk-based approach

Quantitative risk assessment: a well-defined approach (FAO/WHO, 2021)

Science-based decisions in microbial food safety

Who conducts risk assessments?

- Research teams
- Food safety agencies to answer **risk manager's questions**

e.g.

“What is the effect of introducing a microbiological criterium?”

“What is the number of cases associated with this pathogen/food?”

“What time/temperature conditions control the risk?”

...

Science-based decisions in microbial food safety

Quantitative risk assessment: a basis for taking risk-based decision for risk manager

Risk management metrics in the food production chain:

- ALOP: Appropriate Level of Protection
- FSO: Food Safety Objective
- PO: Performance Objective
- PC: Performance Criterion
- MC: Microbiological criteria

More than “risk”: burden, cost, ...

Science-based decisions in microbial food safety

Quantitative risk assessment: it's modelling!

A lot of resources needed

Data

published literature,
government reports,
national surveillance data,
food control laboratories,
public health laboratories,
food producers, industry, retailers
consumer consumption data
Epidemiological surveys
Outbreak investigations
Expert opinion...

Models

Predictive microbiology models,
Dose response,
variability distributions, uncertainty...

Challenges in QMRA

How can I make it easier for others (and myself)?

Table 2 Growth rate and growth/no-growth models evaluated in the study

Models	Equations	Descriptions	References
CM _n	$CM_n(X) = \begin{cases} 0, & X \leq X_{min} \\ \frac{(X-X_{min})(X-X_{min})^n}{(X_{opt}-X_{min})^{n+1} \left\{ (X_{opt}-X_{min})(X-X_{opt}) - (X_{opt}-X_{max})[(n-1)X_{opt} + X_{min} - nX] \right\}}, & X_{min} < X < X_{max} \end{cases}$	Effect of T , pH and a_w on μ_{max}	Rosso <i>et al.</i> (1995)
SR _n	$SR_n(X) = \begin{cases} 0, & X \leq X_{min} \\ \left(\frac{X-X_{min}}{X_{opt}-X_{min}} \right)^n, & X_{min} < X \leq X_{opt} \end{cases}$	Effect of T , pH and a_w on μ_{max}	Ratkowsky <i>et al.</i> (1982), Zwietering <i>et al.</i> (1991)
SR	$SR(c) = \begin{cases} 1 - \frac{c}{MIC}, & c < MIC \\ 0, & c \geq MIC \end{cases}$	Effect of preservatives on μ_{max}	Devlieghere <i>et al.</i> (2001), Giménez and Dalgaard (2004)
P	$P(X) = \begin{cases} 0, & X \leq X_{min} \\ \frac{1-10^{X_{min}-X}}{1-10^{X_{min}-X_{opt}}}, & X_{min} < X \leq X_{opt} \end{cases}$	Effect of pH on μ_{max}	Presser <i>et al.</i> (1997), Tienungoon <i>et al.</i> (2000)
Interactions	$X_{i,min} = X_{i,opt} - (X_{i,opt} - X_{i,min}^0) \left[\prod_j \left(\frac{1-c_j}{MIC_j} \right) - \sum_{k \neq i} \left(\frac{X_{k,opt} - X_k}{X_{k,opt} - X_{k,min}^0} \right) \right]^{1/2}$	Effect of environmental factors on minimal cardinal values	Augustin and Carlier (2000b)
Interactions	$MIC_j = MIC_j^0 \left[1 - \frac{\sum_i \left(\frac{X_{i,opt} - X_i}{X_{i,opt} - X_{i,min}^0} \right)}{\prod_{i \neq j} \left(\frac{1-c_i}{MIC_i^0} \right)} \right]$	Effect of environmental factors on MICs	Augustin and Carlier (2000b)
Interactions	$\xi = \begin{cases} 1, & \psi \leq 0.5 \\ 2(1 - \psi), & 0.5 < \psi < 1 \\ 0, & \psi \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad \psi = \sum_i \frac{\varphi(i)}{2 \prod_{j \neq i} (1 - \varphi(j))}$	Effect of interactions between environmental factors on μ_{max}	Le Marc <i>et al.</i> (2002)
Interactions	$\varphi_{LM}(T) = [1 - \sqrt{CM_2(T)}]^2, \quad \varphi_{LM}(pH) = [1 - CM_1(pH)]^2, \\ \varphi_{LM}(a_w) = [1 - SR_1(a_w)]^3$	Contributions of environmental factors to the interactions	Le Marc (2001), Le Marc <i>et al.</i> (2002)
Model #1	$\mu_{max} = \mu_{opt} CM_2(T) CM_1(pH) SR_1(a_w) SR(nit) SR(phe) SR(CO_2)$	Growth rate model excluding interactions	
Model #2	$\mu_{max} = \mu_{opt} SR_2(T) P(pH) SR_1(a_w) SR(nit) SR(phe) SR(CO_2)$	Growth rate model excluding interactions	
Model #3	$\mu_{max} = \mu_{opt} CM_2^0(T) CM_1^0(pH) SR_1^0(a_w) SR^0(nit) SR^0(phe) SR^0(CO_2)$	Growth rate model including interactions	
Model #4	$\mu_{max} = \mu_{opt} CM_2(T) CM_1(pH) SR_1(a_w) SR(nit) SR(phe) SR(CO_2) \xi(T, pH, a_w, nit, phe, CO_2)$ <p>with $\varphi_{LM}(T), \varphi_{LM}(pH), \varphi_{LM}(a_w), \varphi(nit, phe, CO_2) = [1 - SR(nit) SR(phe) SR(CO_2)]^2$</p>	Growth rate model including interactions	
Model #5	$\mu_{max} = \mu_{opt} CM_2(T) CM_1(pH) SR_1(a_w) SR(nit) SR(phe) SR(CO_2) \xi(T, pH, a_w, nit, phe, CO_2)$ <p>with $\varphi(X) = \left(\frac{X_{opt} - X}{X_{opt} - X_{min}} \right)^3$ where X is T, pH, or a_w, $\varphi(nit, phe, CO_2) = 1 - SR(nit) SR(phe) SR(CO_2)$</p>	Growth rate model including interactions	

Challenges in QMRA

How to maintain code in time?

How to update my input data?

<https://www.slideshare.net/RevolutionAnalytics/rickert-nyr-pres2>

Challenges in QMRA

Reproducibility

Enable other research to check previous conclusions and build upon them

Reproducible science: replicability, repeatability, reliability, robustness, generalizability... transparency, open science, truth

To generate transparent and reusable results, it's essential to document: (Cohen-Boulakia et al. 2017)

- the raw data
- data analysis steps
- procedures and software (code)

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Identification of data and models currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment in EU

- Deployment of a survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment
 - More EJPOH members and broader from September 2020 to June 2021 (>50 people contacted)

Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union – CARE

Objectives of WP4

- To investigate and benchmark the availability and quality of data commonly used for human risk assessments among OHEJP partners, and describe any constraints for making them more easily accessible.
- To promote national participation in initiatives from EU authorities that serve to make high quality data more readily available for human risk assessments.
- For the two bullet points above, to have an early and close coordination with existing data collection initiatives such as EFSA's SIGMA project.

One of the tasks in WP4, which is dealing with (meta-) data, of the EJP-Care project is to **develop and launch a survey** among OHEJP members and broader to identify which data is currently used in human risk assessment.

Next →

Identification of data and models currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment in EU

- Deployment of a survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment
- Information about existing QMRA and data from the last 5 years

Identification of data and models currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment in EU

- Deployment of a survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment
 - Are the data available?

Data identified

3 sources of data :

- Data from literature | 88 %
- Data produced by the risk assessor/organization | 72 %
- Data from a scientific network | 18 %

16 QMRA have been published = AVAILABLE DATA SOURCES

“availability” yes but different from Machine-readable data

Example: <https://www.anses.fr/en/content/raw-data-anses-inca-3-study-now-available>

Identification of data and models currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment in EU

- Deployment of a survey on (meta-)data relevant for risk assessment

- Are the models available?

They are described in details, but not truly “available”

Some exceptions

EFSA gQMRA model for listeriosis (10.5281/zenodo.1117742)

The screenshot shows the Zenodo repository page for the EFSA gQMRA model. The page header includes the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and navigation links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The main content area displays the title 'Listeria monocytogenes generic Quantitative Microbiological Risk Assessment (gQMRA) model' and the date 'January 24, 2018'. The page is categorized as 'Software' and 'Open Access'. On the right side, there are statistics for '463 views' and '792 downloads'. Below the title, the authors are listed: 'EFSA Panel on Biological Hazards (BIOHAZ); Ricci, Antonia; Allende, Ana; Bolton, Declan; Chemaly, Marianne; Davies, Robert; Fernández Escámez, Pablo Salvador; Girones, Rosina; Herman, Lieve; Koutsoumanis, Konstantinos; Nørrung, Birgit; Robertson, Lucy; Ru, Giuseppe; Sanaa, Moez; Simmons, Marion; Skandamis, Panagiotis; Snary, Emma; Speybroeck, Niko; Ter Kuile, Benno; Threlfall, John; Wahlström, Helene; Takkinen, Johanna; Wagner, Martin; Arcella, Davide; Da Silva Felicio, Maria Teresa; Georgiadis, Marios; Messens, Winy; Lindqvist, Roland'. A short description follows: 'This model was developed and applied by the EFSA Working Group on Listeria monocytogenes contamination of ready-to-eat (RTE) foods during the preparatory work on the Scientific Opinion 'Listeria monocytogenes contamination of ready-to-eat foods and the risk for human health in the EU' (see 10.2903/sp.efsa.2017.EN-1252)'. A longer description states: 'This model was based on the model developed by Pérez-Rodríguez et al. (2017) (see 10.2903/sp.efsa.2017.EN-1252) with some adaptations and improvements in order to examine the possible effect of factors/hypotheses on the increase of human invasive listeriosis incidence rates in the EU/EEA. It is a quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA) model, developed in R. The model is generic in the sense that the model allows the inclusion of more or fewer RTE food categories and subpopulations without changing the R code. As the inputs are provided in structured Microsoft Excel'. On the right side, there are two boxes: 'Indexed in OpenAIRE' and 'Publication date: January 24, 2018'. At the bottom right, the DOI is displayed as 'DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1117742'.

Data available and potentially usable in QMRA

Some relevant sources of data:

According to **Directive 2003/99/EC** reporting information of foodborne and waterborne outbreaks (FBOs) is mandatory for EU Member States. Please note that the data visualized are affected by the selected filters. If you have any questions on this dashboard, please contact zoonoses@efsa.europa.eu

User guide

Foodborne outbreaks - story map

Data available and potentially usable in QMRA

→ EFSA and ECDC developed tools and supported projects in order to promote exchange and interoperability of knowledge

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Surveillance Atlas of Infectious Diseases

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Sharing data

Data management plan

(Source: Utrecht University, research data management support)

Sharing data

Data repositories:

Data journals: e.g Data in Brief,
Scientific Data

Table 1. DataCite Metadata Schema properties.

Mandatory	Recommended	Optional
Identifier	Subject	Language
Creator	Contributor	Alternate Identifier
Title	Date	Size
Publisher	Related Identifier	Format
Publication Year	Description	Version
Resource Type	Geolocation	Rights

Supplementary materials

Where are the data?

Nature Methods now requires data availability statements to be supplied with research papers.

Sharing data

Data repositories for predictive microbiology

ComBase Home About Donate data FAQ Contact us

ComBase users say...

"I find ComBase absolutely essential to my teaching, research and outreach activities. I seldom go for more than a week without consulting it for solving a variety of food safety problems."
Donald Schaffner
Distinguished Professor and Extension Specialist, Rutgers University

"ComBase is a tool that helps our business to predict microbial responses in foodstuffs to support better and faster product and process design, and to assess and manage risks to consumer health. It is of great value to us."
Alejandro Amezcua
PhD Science Leader, Microbiological Risk Assessment & Food Safety, Unilever

"We find ComBase a very useful tool and use it for a variety of activities including shelf life determinations, maximum run lengths for how long a line can run before it requires cleaning and to help define appropriate conditions for microbial challenge tests."
Heinz

The **ComBase Browser** enables you to search thousands of microbial growth and survival curves that have been collated in research establishments and from publications

The **ComBase Predictive Models** are a collection of software tools based on ComBase data to predict the growth or inactivation of microorganisms

[Login/Register](#) 58,500 + records | 70,000 + users

Supported by **USDA** United States Department of Agriculture
Agricultural Research Service

A Web Resource for Quantitative and Predictive Food Microbiology

It includes:

- ✓ A systematically formatted database of quantified microbial responses to the food environment with more than 60,000 records

New updates

[Click here](#) to see the new updates to data and features

New online models

Sharing data

Data repositories for prevalence, concentration data

<https://fsqa.esa.ipb.pt/>

PATHOGENS in FOODS database

HOME OVERVIEW SUPPORT NEWS FAQ CONTACT US EXPLORE DATABASE ACCESS SYSTEM

PATHOGENS IN FOODS

THE WEB RESOURCES ENABLES YOU TO:

- SEARCH FOR DETECTION AND ENUMERATION DATA OF PATHOGENS IN FOODS
- OBTAIN OVERALL VISUAL AND DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSES
- GENERATE SUMMARISATION STATISTICS OF DATA SELECTIONS

Sharing QMRA models

Supplementary materials

Non specific code repositories

Specific repositories : e.g. EFSA knowledge Junction

```
5431 #####
5432 #####
5433 # Part 1: Aggregated analysis
5434 #####
5435 #####
5436 remove(list=ls())
5437 # Read in the data (this dataset was created from the initial dataset)
5438 tmp <- read.csv("totals.csv", header=T, sep = ";")
5439 L <- ts(tmp[,3], start=c(2008,1), freq=12)
5440 L2 <- ts(10000000*tmp[,3]/tmp[,4], start=c(2008,1), freq=12)
5441 # Check the total number of cases that should be 14002
5442 sum(L)
5443 # Source in the pests.r code for the PAR models
5444 # Can be found in http://www.utdallas.edu/~pbrandt/code/pests.r
5445 source("pests.r")
5446 # Plot the data and check the AR dynamics: Figure in the report
5447 par(mfcol=c(2,1), mai=c(0.9,1.1,0.3,0.15))
5448 plot(L, main="", ylab="Cases", xlab="")
5449 plot(L2, main="", ylab="Cases/10000000")
5450 counts.acf(L, main="", ylab="Correlations")
5451 # Very seasonal set of correlations, so PAR(p) is not going to work
5452 # and these are not really rare counts that would follow a Poisson process
5453 # Non-FAR models tried here too.
5454 # Arima models checked but Seasonal part process that is non-stationary,
5455 # since the seasonal AR ~ 1 and the seasonal MA > |0.5|
5456 # Consider a non-parametric state-space decomposition: Figure not in the report
5457 plot(stl(L, s.window=13))
5458 # Seems to have strong, maybe changing trend and a well-defined seasonal
5459 # A DLM seems appropriate
5460 # Load the library / package before executing the following line.
5461 library(dlm)
5462 level0 <- L[1]
```

And are the tools available?

We take the opportunity to remind our readers of the materials sharing policy at *Nature Methods*.

Sharing QMRA models

Sharing through dedicated tools:

e.g. JEMRA FAO/WHO

Risk Management Tool for the Control of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* in Chicken Meat

(Version 1.0)

English ▾

[Home](#) | [Process Flow List](#) | [Tutorial](#) | [User Guide](#) | [Documents](#) | [Send Comments](#) | [Login](#)

Welcome

This web site provides access to a risk management simulation tool based on the Codex Guidelines for the Control of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* in Chicken Meat.

The tool can describe the complete production-to-consumption flow path described in the guidelines. These models are referred to as process flows. Users may investigate one or both pathogens and determine which steps to include in the process flow.

The tool is designed to compute the residual risk between a baseline process flow and a process flow applying selected interventions as outlined in the guidelines. The residual risk measure may be used to evaluate the overall effectiveness of the applied interventions.

FAO and WHO would also like to express their appreciation to all those who have [contributed](#) to the development of this tool.

Please review the [Guidelines](#), [user guide](#), [tutorial](#), [supporting documents](#) and [disclaimer](#) before using this tool.

Sharing QMRA models

Sharing through dedicated tools:

e.g.

FDA-iRISK® 4.2 Home Risk Models Reports Repositories Help

Home

FDA-iRISK is a web-based system designed to analyze data concerning microbial and chemical hazards in food and return an estimate of the resulting health burden on a population level.

The data required to execute this analysis include the food and its associated consumption data and processing/preparation methods, the hazard and its dose-response curve, and the anticipated health effects of the hazard when ingested by humans. Each of these elements contributes an essential piece of information to the model on which the final estimate of risk is based.

When you register, you will be assigned your own personal workspace in which to model food/hazard risk scenarios. You may also share this workspace with others to view. Note: your model and data are only accessible by you, unless you choose to share them with another user. FDA does not have access to your information. See [privacy disclaimer](#) via [Register](#) link below.

For a complete description, review the [Quick Start Tutorial](#) and [User Guide](#) on the [Help](#) page before beginning.

For a list of major changes from Version 4.0, view the [What's New in FDA-iRISK 4.2](#) page.

Please [Login](#) or [Register](#).

Suggested Citation

Where the FDA-iRISK system is used in risk assessment research and other food safety activities, reference to the system should be made as follows:

Food and Drug Administration Center for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition (FDA/CFSAN), Joint Institute for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition (JIFSAN) and Risk Sciences International (RSI). 2021. FDA-iRISK® version 4.2. FDA CFSAN. College Park, Maryland. Available at <https://irisk.foodrisk.org/>.

Improve the reusability of data and models in QMRA

SOFTWARE REUSE

3

REUSABILITY [DEFINITION]

Reusability is a general engineering principle whose importance derives from the desire to **avoid duplication** and to **capture commonality** in undertaking classes of inherently similar tasks.

Source: Peter Wegner, "Capital-Intensive Software Technology", in Chapter 3 of *Software Reusability, Volume I : Concepts and Models*, ACM Press, 1989.

Software reusability is the degree to which a software module or other work product can be used in more than one software system.

Reusable: pertaining to a software module or other work product that can be used in more than one computer program or software system.

Improve the reusability of data and models in QMRA

The RAKIP initiative (BfR/DTU/ANSES)

Improve the reusability of data and model in QMRA

RAKIP Initiative

Define **terms** and **concepts** :

- Speak the **same language**

<https://goo.gl/b4ADho>

Define **metadata schema**

<https://goo.gl/PE4ysP>

Define a **controlled vocabulary**

- From SSD (EFSA), PMM-Lab, ICRA, FOODON, RIS format etc.
- Create vocabulary if necessary

<https://goo.gl/wbFoZU>

Improve reusability of data and models in QMRA

RAKIP - FSK-ML Format

➤ Objective:

Experimental data and mathematical models from the domain of predictive microbial modeling and QMRA can be saved and encoded in a software independent manner

<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/fsk-ml-food-safety-knowledge-markup-language/>

➤ Standardized file format (« .fskx »)

- Includes also model code in specific script-based programming languages (currently R; Python, KNIME and others under development)

<https://knime.bfr.berlin/landingpage/RAKIP-Model-Repository/>

Plenty of improvements coming in with EJP OH

CARE: Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union

ORION: One health suRveillance Initiative on harmOnization of data collection and interpretation

COHESIVE : One Health Structure In Europe Surveillance data

RADAR

DISCOVER

MATRIX

NOVA

...

Conclusion – Take home message

Quantitative microbial risk assessment is today: a concrete tool to make decisions

Need for transparency – reproducibility – reusability

Extra work to make data available, check and annotate models

Resources

Capacity

Motivation

Linkages

Thank you for your
attention!

